

Materials for 3D Printed Metal and Metal-Ion Batteries

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The review provides an overview of the latest innovations, trends, and challenges in the field of 3D-printed metal and metal-ion batteries. It focuses on the materials used in the printing of batteries, including electrodes, electrolytes, and other electroactive components. Compared to other high-quality reviews on the topic, this review provides a broader selection of materials that are expected to gain attention in the next few years, such as redox-active polymers and metal-organic frameworks. This work gives an overview and insight

into the latest trends in printing techniques as well as a statistical review of their uses and strengths. We have also gathered the latest works done for each of the material types, and we have taken the opportunity to put them in context and use them to exemplify in which direction is the field going. The review concludes with a critical view of the challenges ahead and a discussion of the direction that the field is taking as well as the external factors that might help to define its future.

1. Introduction

The rising demand for portable consumer electronics and the impending widespread use of electric vehicles (EVs) have led to the need for sustainable and more efficient fabrication methods for electrochemical energy storage devices (EESDs).^[1] Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have been the primary energy storage system since their introduction in 1991, especially for portable electronics like computers, cell phones, and cameras. Modern LIBs are a well-established and mature technology, with production methods that have been optimized for industrial scale. The most used method for preparing electrodes is slurry casting. This method is based on simple and easily scalable steps, which partially explains its widespread adoption.^[2,3] However, electrodes deposited by slurry casting are at most 100 μm thick.^[2] Modern batteries are also regulated in specific sizes and usually restricted to specific form factors such as cylindrical, coin-cell, rectangular, and prismatic types.^[4] Therefore, battery production by slurry casting is not an ideal process for novel applications such as the Internet of Things (IoT)

concept, which typically require flexibility, miniaturization, easy integration, and adaptable geometries.^[3] On the other hand, printing batteries allow for a cost-effective, customized, large-area, and high-volume layer deposition. To be considered a printed battery, at least one or more of its components (current collectors, electrodes, or separator/electrolyte) must be produced using printing technologies.^[3] These printing methods include ink-jet printing (IJ), screen-printing, and flexographic printing, among others. Some manufacturing techniques allow the layering of material creating complex and controllable 3D structures, this is generally known as 3D printing or additive manufacturing (AM).^[5–8] In recent years, this approach has rapidly developed into a research field that offers methodologies and solutions for various technological applications, including energy storage. The increasing adoption of additive manufacturing is revolutionizing the production of wearable electronics and EESDs such as batteries, supercapacitors, and fuel cells. This surge can be attributed to its outstanding process versatility, precise control over geometrical aspects, and potential to reduce costs and material waste.^[7,9] In this comprehensive review, major AM processes like inkjet printing, direct ink writing (DIW), fused deposition modeling (FDM), and selective laser sintering/melting (SLS) along with possible configurations and architectures, are elaborately discussed. The application of 3D-printed energy storage devices in wearable electronics, IoT-based devices, and electric vehicles is also mentioned in the review. Extensive research and continuous progress in this field are expected to enhance the longevity, industrial scalability, and electrochemical performance of 3D-printed energy storage devices in the future.^[6] These include low waste generation, higher flexibility in the choice of electrode substrate, and one-step manufacturing in the micro to macro-scale. As digital technologies, AM manufacturing also provides significant versatility and freedom in electrode design for complex structures with controlled thicknesses. This provides a significant advantage over planar devices, enabling an increase in areal capacity without sacrificing power density due to improved ion flow.^[10] This results in a separation of the energy and power density of the batteries, making it easier to

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customize the batteries for specific applications. Compared to 2D printing techniques, AM offers more sustainable approaches due to its flexibility in the type and amount of solvent used for the ink formulation. Furthermore, it expands the range of printable materials, including polymer composites, metal alloys, concrete, ceramics, and more. This facilitates the printing of not only the electrodes but also the electrolytes, current collectors, and casings, reducing prototyping costs and streamlining the device. Cost efficiency is a significant advantage for both emerging applications and new battery chemistries, accelerating innovation cycles and the lab-to-fab process. Among the various types of possible 3D printed architectures, the most commonly reported are stacked, interdigitated, and fibrous structures (see Figure 1).^[11] Stackable batteries have the same architecture as conventional LIBs, but they are composed of printed components which can have non-conventional shapes. The interdigitated configuration is a popular architecture known for its high aspect ratios, which optimize ion transport and enhance energy density. Finally, fiber-shaped or 1D batteries typically have a helical or parallel structure. Although they have lower capacities and power densities, their mechanical properties make them attractive for wearable and flexible technologies.^[11] Electrodes are the most commonly printed battery component, but printed electrolytes and current collectors are also gaining popularity. These architectures, along with new fabrication techniques, offer numerous application opportunities, ways to overcome material limitations, and integration options.

This review provides an overview of the latest innovations, trends, and challenges in this fast-paced field clearly and concisely. While there are already high-quality reviews available on printing techniques and mechanisms,^[12] design,^[4] and applications,^[8] this review will focus on materials. We have expanded the range of materials compared to other

Figure 1. All-printed batteries (APT) main structural configurations, along with device properties. Reproduced with permission.^[11] Copyright (2023) Wiley-VCH.

reviews,^[13,14] including those that have received less attention in the field, and it is expected that due to the shift of society towards sustainability, their popularity will increase in the next few years. This is the case, for instance, with redox-active organic materials. Additionally, we provide an overview of the latest advances and trends in other electroactive materials, printing technologies, and printed electrolyte choices. We conclude this review with a statistical analysis of the field and a critical assessment of the challenges ahead.

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2. Printing Techniques

Although there are many additive manufacturing methods, not all can be employed in the fabrication of electrochemically active parts due to the material requirements of EESDs. Four big families of printing techniques can be identified based on how the material is fixed in place. These are: light-based, filament-based, powder-based and jetting-based.^[12] In addition, there is a fifth family known as template-assisted printing, which includes a variety of deposition techniques that traditionally would not be considered additive manufacturing methods, such as spray coating or screen printing. However, by the use of templates, they can produce 3D structures through the subsequent application of layers.

In the following lines the strengths and weaknesses of each technique are discussed in the context of printed batteries and in Figure 2 is provided a qualitative radar map that broadly gathers the advantages of the mentioned families.

2.1. Light-Based

This family of techniques is based on the use of light sources to cure resins or suspensions, as shown in Figure 3A.^[12] The most common technique among these is SLA, which employs photocurable resins that react to ultraviolet (UV) light. This technique offers high resolution and good interconnection between layers.^[17] However, the properties of the cured materials are not always compatible with the requirements of the EESDs and thus, this type of technique is generally employed just to build 3D polymeric substrates that are later covered or coated with active materials. This strategy has been used to prepare both electrodes^[18] and solid electrolytes

Figure 2. Radar map of the described five families of printing techniques. The scoring of each family was done based on the works of references.^[4,14–16]

Figure 3. Main 3D printing techniques families (A to E) with their respective schematic representation and literature examples. Example in (A) reproduced with permission of.^[19] Copyright (2018) The Royal Society of Chemistry. Example in (B) reproduced with permission of Ref. [29] Copyright (2023) Wiley. Example in (C) reproduced with permission of Ref. [27]. Copyright (2021) Elsevier. Example in (D) reproduced with permission of Ref. [30] Copyright (2019) Wiley. Example in (E) reproduced with permission of Ref. [37]. Copyright (2021) Elsevier.

(SEs).^[19] There are alternative options for using stereolithography (SLA) in printed batteries. For example, one of the most common polymeric SEs, polyethylene oxide (PEO), is photocurable and, therefore suitable for use in light-based techniques.^[20] Another approach is to include photocurable resins in the inks. After printing, the piece is subjected to a thermal treatment to remove the cured resins. However, this is

only possible with materials that have high thermal stability such as ceramic electrolytes as the ones printed by Sabato *et al.*^[21]

2.2. Filament-Based

Filament techniques are the most commonly used for fabricating 3D EESDs. These techniques involve depositing semisolid yarns through a nozzle that solidifies shortly after deposition (Figure 3B). Among this family of techniques, we find two main approaches, FDM and DIW. FDM involves depositing thermoplastic filaments that are heated to a semi-molten state at the nozzle and solidified upon deposition in the printing bed. Although is the most extended 3D printed methodology, its application in the field of printed batteries is hindered by the limited range of printable materials. The most extended strategy for this technique is based on mixing the active materials with a thermoplastic such as polylactic acid (PLA), acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), or polycarbonate (PC). However, the low conductivity of these matrixes restricts the selection of active materials and the amount of thermoplastic that can be used in the blends. This technique has been widely used for the printing of electrodes (Table 1) with comparable capacities, rates, and conductivities to those fabricated by slurry casting. This performance is due to the substitution of the binder with the thermoplastic which also allows a solvent-free deposition.^[22,23] FDM has also been used to print electrolytes. In this case, the most common strategy is the infiltration of pre-printed PLA-based membranes with liquid electrolytes forming quasi-solid electrolytes (QSEs).^[24] However, there are also true solid-state electrolytes printed by FDM based on solid polymeric electrolytes (SPEs). In these cases, PLA is combined with a SPE such as PEO and lithium salts to form the electrolyte, as in the case of Ragonés *et al.*^[25]

On the other hand, DIW is a printing technique based on the extrusion of visco-elastic ink through a nozzle. DIW allows the use of a wide variety of active materials and additives.^[14] The end composition and microstructure of the electrodes are mostly the same as in the slurry-based depositions traditionally employed in industrial battery production.^[15] The critical aspect of this deposition technique is the ink formulation and its rheological properties. The inks must exhibit shear-thinning behavior to flow properly through the nozzle but then maintain the filament-like shape once deposited. The great flexibility of this deposition technique has allowed the printing of numerous materials for cathodes, anodes, and SEs (Table 1), including even ceramic electrolytes.^[26]

2.3. Powder-Based

This family of techniques is based on the sintering or melting of powders. High-energy lasers are projected on powder-containing beds to sinter the materials layer by layer until achieving the desired shape (Figure 3C). The most common technique is SLS, and it is usually used for the sintering of polymers and

ceramics. Although it has been demonstrated its use for batteries, its material selection is still complex compared to filament-based techniques, it produces residual stress on the material, the control of the microstructure properties of the final material is still a challenge and the throughput is low.^[8,12] It has been reported its use for the preparation of thick, solvent-free Lithium Nickel Cobalt Aluminum Oxide, (LiNi_{0.8}Co_{0.15}Al_{0.05}O₂, NCA) cathodes, although due to the low maturity of the technique in the field, the obtained performance was very low (16 mAh g⁻¹ compared to the nominal 167.7 mAh g⁻¹ obtained by slurry-based techniques).^[27] Similarly, Chen *et al.*^[28] prepared a magnesium anode for LIBs through SLS, obtaining relatively low performances.

2.4. Jetting-Based

Jetting techniques are based on the deposition of low-viscosity inks through small nozzles that move along the surface creating thin layers (Figure 3D). Resolution tends to be very high although it depends on the jetting mechanism, nozzle size, rheology, and surface tension of the inks used for deposition.^[16]

The two more representative exponents of jetting-based techniques are IJP and aerosol jet printing (AJP).

IJP is based on the ejection of droplets onto a surface through a nozzle. It can be continuous inkjet (CIJ) or drop-on-demand (DOD).^[4] IJP is very flexible in terms of printable materials and only requires a stable solution with a particle size compatible with the nozzle to avoid clogging. The control of IJP deposition is based on the ink formulation and its interaction with the substrate,^[8] and its resolution is typically in the 10–150 μm range although higher resolutions have been achieved.^[4,16] The main disadvantages of IJP are its low throughput and inability to produce self-standing structures, which limits its use mainly to thin film applications. This is reflected in the literature, where films tend to be just a few microns thick, which limits the usable particle size^[31] and favors the use of nanomaterials.^[32] IJP has been extensively used in the preparation of both thin film cathodes^[32,33] and anodes.^[34,35]

AJP is a contactless technique that achieves resolutions in the range of 10 μm by jetting material through the spraying of ink with pressurized gas. The annular sheath gas flow focuses the stream of ink, allowing for deposition over any substrate regardless of surface roughness.^[36] This technique also enables the deposition of a wide variety of materials with looser ink requirements compared to IJP. To increase its throughput, prevent pooling, and achieve thicker electrodes, lasers can be used to assist in the solidification of inks.^[30] However, controlling the microstructure can be challenging and may result in highly porous structures.^[15] This technique has gained recent attention and there are examples of printed anodes,^[15] cathodes,^[30,37,38] and solid-polymeric electrolytes.^[38]

Table 1. Summary of representative electrodes printed by different 3D printing techniques and available data from commercial electrodes. Materials within the same electrode are separated by //, while separates different electrodes.

Materials	Category	Technique	Chemistry	Capacity	Cycles	Capacity retention (%)	Year	Ref.
LFP	Commercial	Conventional	Li-ion	170 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C Thickness = 70 μm Mass loading = 7.3 mg cm ²	-	-	-	[43]
NMC811	Commercial	Conventional	Li-ion	200 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C Thickness = 16 μm Mass loading = 10 mg cm ²	-	-	-	[43]
LMO	Commercial	Conventional	Li-ion	100 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C Thickness = 60 μm Mass loading = 12.5 mg cm ²	-	-	-	[43]
LCO	Commercial	Conventional	Li-ion	160 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C Thickness = 65 μm Mass loading = 12.5 mg cm ²	-	-	-	[43]
LTO	Commercial	Conventional	Li-ion	165 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C Thickness = 60 μm Mass loading = 7.6 mg cm ²	-	-	-	[43]
Graphite	Commercial	Conventional	Li-ion	370 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C Thickness = 60 μm Mass loading = 6.5 mg cm ²	-	-	-	[43]
LFP	Standard	FDM	Li-ion	116 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	-	-	2024	[23]
LFP	Standard	FDM	Li-ion	150 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.5 C	100 at 1 C	-	2023	[22]
LFP	Standard	FDM	Li-ion	145 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.5 C	150 at 1 C	100	2018	[44]
LFP	Standard	FDM	Li-ion	160 mAh g ⁻¹ at 50 mA g ⁻¹	30	97	2017	[45]
LFP/PLA/CNT	Standard + Nanomaterials	FDM	Li-ion	156 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C	200 at 0.5 C	~95	2021	[46]
LFP/MgO	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	160 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.33 C	800 at 1 C	96	2022	[47]
LFP	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	155 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.33 C	-	-	2020	[48]
LFP	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	160 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	-	-	2019	[49]
LFP/MWCNTs	Standard + Nanomaterials	DIW	Li-ion	150 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.5 C	500 at 5 C	~80	2021	[50]
LFP/PEDOT:PSS/CMC	Standard + Organic	DIW	Li-ion	2 layers: 150.9 mAh g ⁻¹ 12 layers: 100 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.5 C	100 at 0.2 C	Over 80	2021	[51]
LFP	Printed electrolyte	AJP	Li-ion	136 mAh g ⁻¹ 0.5 C	30	-	2019	[30]
LFP	Printed electrolyte	AJP	Li-ion	115 mAh g ⁻¹ at 1 C	50	-	2019	[37]
LFP	Printed electrolyte	AJP	Solid State Li	120 mAh g ⁻¹ at 1 C (60 °C)	150	-	2023	[38]
LFP - LTO	Standard	FDM	Li-ion	140 mAh g ⁻¹ at 50 mA g ⁻¹	0	81	2017	[62]
NMC	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	192 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	50 at C/3	89.7	2023	[52]
NMC	Standard	Screen printing	Li-ion	170 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	100 at 1 C	50	2023	[53]
Li _{1-x} K _{0.05} Mn _{0.54} Ni _{0.13} Co _{0.13} O ₂	Printed electrolyte	IJP	Li-ion	240 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.01 C	70	70%	2020	[33]
LMO/POPD/OD Carbon	Standard + Organic	FDM + electrodeposition	Li-ion	69 mAh g ⁻¹ at ~1.2 C	200	84.4	2021	[54]
LMO	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	103 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	30 at 0.1 C	100	2020	[55]

Materials	Category	Technique	Chemistry	Capacity	Cycles	Capacity retention (%)	Year	Ref.
LCO	Standard	FDM	Li-ion	83 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	–	–	2023	[56]
V ₂ O ₅ /Mxene	Nanomaterial	IJP	Li-ion	321 mAh g ⁻¹ at 1 C	680 at 10.5 C	91.8	2021	[32]
NaMnO ₂	Standard	DIW	Na-ion	120 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C	–	–	2023	[57]
LTO	Standard	FDM	Li-ion	148 mAh g ⁻¹ at 50 mA g ⁻¹	30	75	2017	[58]
LTO	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	160 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	100 at 1 C	82.6	2022	[59]
LTO	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	~140 mAh g ⁻¹ at 1 C	30	–	2019	[60]
LTO	Standard	IJP	Li-ion	125 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.5 C	680	91.8	2021	[34]
LTO	Printed electrolyte	AJP	Li-ion	~115 mAh g ⁻¹ at 1 C	–	–	2023	[15]
Graphite	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	350 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	100 at 0.2 C	100	2021	[61]
Graphite	Standard	DIW	Li-ion	345 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	100 at 0.2 C	95	2022	[62]
Graphene	Nanomaterials	IJP	Li-ion	~942 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C	100 at 2 C	~87	2021	[63]
Si/PEDOT:PSS/PEG	Nanomaterials+Organic	DLP	Li-ion	~1600 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.1 C	125	72	2022	[64]
Si/PLA/Graphene/CB-doped Polypyrrole	Nanomaterials+Organic	FDM	Li-ion	345 mAh g ⁻¹ at 20 mA g ⁻¹	350 at 20 mA g ⁻¹	96	2021	[65]
Si/rGO	Nanomaterials	FDM	Li-ion	16.2 mAh cm ⁻²	70 at 200 mA g ⁻¹	75.4	2022	[66]
Si/PEDOT:PSS	Nanomaterials+Organic	IJP	Li-ion	~2300 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	100	61	2017	[34]
MoS ₂ /rGO	Nanomaterials	3D freeze-printing (3DFP)	Na-ion	429 mAh g ⁻¹ at 100 mA g ⁻¹	–	–	2019	[58]
Si/rGO-LFP/rGO	Nanomaterials	FDM	Li-ion	~100 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	140 at 0.2 C	~62	2022	[67]
TPU/LFP-TPU/LTO	Standard+Organic	FDM	Li-ion	100 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.33 C	50	–	2019	[66]
Disperse blue 134 anthraquinone (DB)	Organic	AJP	Li-ion	~70 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	–	–	2019	[68]
DB-DB	Organic	AJP	TFSI-ion	~70 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	–	–	–	–
PAQS	Organic	Stencil/screen printing	Li and TFSI ions	~60 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	250	62	–	–
PAQS-LTO	Organic	Stencil/screen printing	Li-ion	117 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	100 at 0.2 C	84	2021	[69]
PAQS-LTO	Organic	Stencil/screen printing	Na-ion	127.6 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	–	–	–	–
PAQS-LTO	Organic	R2R Stencil/screen printing	Li-ion	64 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	500 at 0.5 C	73	–	–
1D Carbon/PAA doped PANI	Organic	FDM+electrodeposition	Li-ion	57 mAh g ⁻¹ at 0.2 C	100 at 0.2 C	61	–	–
1D Carbon/PAA doped PANI	Organic	FDM+electrodeposition	Zn-ion	214.6 mAh g ⁻¹ at 400 mA g ⁻¹	1000	78.1	2022	[70]

2.5. Template Assisted

As mentioned earlier in this section, templates enable the production of 3D structures using techniques that typically are not considered additive manufacturing techniques. This is the case of 3D screen printing, which involves the application of inks or powders with the aid of a mask that can change its shape as it moves in the Z direction (Figure 3E). These are later sintered or dried, retaining their structure and achieving resolutions as low as 50 μm .^[39] This technique has been used to prepare various types of objects, from small detailed metallic pieces^[40] to layer-by-layer engineered drugs.^[41] In the field of batteries, this methodology is behind the patent filed by Blackstone Technology GmbH for the 3D printing of solid-state batteries.^[42]

3. Electroactive Materials for 3D-Printed Electrodes

One of the main attractiveness that 3D printing has for battery manufacturing comes from the limitation of current manufacturing methods to maximize simultaneously energy and power density. While in planar devices increasing electrode thickness always results in reduced power density due to slower kinetics, by smart 3D patterning is possible to overcome this limitation. This opens a whole new set of possibilities where materials that were underperforming in planar devices can find new uses. In this section, we explore the latest trends and works done with standard battery materials, in which we include cathode and anode materials but also, we give special consideration to active materials and additives in the nanoscale. Afterward, we cover a very incipient yet important family of materials that are the redox active organic materials, which are gaining momentum in the light of sustainability considerations.

3.1. Standard Electrode Materials

Commercially available LiBs use alloys, metal oxides, and carbon-based materials as electrodes. These materials are chosen for their balance between cost, performance, and safety. However, conventional electrodes encounter significant challenges, such as the requirement for rapid charging of electric vehicles^[71] and high areal capacity to enhance overall energy density.^[72] Recently, 3D printing technologies have shown potential in enhancing electrode materials, providing opportunities for improved performance and design flexibility. The following sections provide an overview of relevant examples of successfully 3D-printed cathodes and anode materials for battery applications. Due to their importance in the development of EESDs, an additional section is included to highlight the main advantages of nanomaterials in additive manufacturing and energy storage.

3.1.1. Printed Cathode Materials

Among the positive electrode materials, lithium ferrophosphate (LFP) has a low theoretical capacity (170 mAh g^{-1}) and voltage (3.65 V vs Li/Li⁺). However, it has been widely used for LiBs owing to its good thermal stability, high cyclability, and low content on critical raw materials.^[73] Therefore, LFP is a suitable candidate for testing 3D printing technologies where sustainability is a factor as important as performance. For example, Sun *et al.*^[74] were pioneers in the use of 3D-printed electrode materials. They used FDM to fabricate a microbattery with LFP, achieving initial capacities of 160 mAh g^{-1} at 1 C in a half-cell and performing 30 cycles in a full cell. Wang *et al.* further demonstrated the versatility of 3D printing in battery applications by using FDM to prepare an all-fiber battery with LFP/lithium titanate (LTO) electrodes. This resulted in a flexible and wearable battery with an initial capacity of 110 mAh g^{-1} and capacity retention of 81 % after 30 cycles at a current density of 50 mA g^{-1} .^[58] FDM was also used to prepare thick LFP electrodes for high energy density applications delivering 140 mAh g^{-1} for 150 cycles at 1 C. Electrodes prepared by FDM can be up to 1500 μm thick, which is significantly greater than the thickness of electrodes prepared by conventional techniques.^[75] However, longer cycling performance tests should be carried out to compare with the cycling performance of conventional electrodes^[76] and reach the autonomy requirements of commercial applications.^[77] Nevertheless, these findings indicate that 3D printing allows for the preparation of various battery configurations by using commercially available materials (Figure 4). Finally, several attempts were also made to prepare LFP electrodes by DIW.^[47–49,78] However, the work done by Li *et al.*^[50] was remarkable because they were able to prepare a high areal capacity and power density electrode by DIW and freeze-drying processes. The obtained grid structure allowed the electrode to deliver an initial rate capacity of 140 mAh g^{-1} at 1 C and capacity retention of 80% after 500 cycles at a high rate (5 C).

As previously stated, LFP has a low theoretical capacity and voltage; thus, making it unsuitable for high-energy and high-power applications. On the other hand, lithium cobalt oxide (LCO) electrodes have higher voltages (4.2 V vs Li/Li⁺) than LFP and have been the main industrial choice for portable applications.^[79] Therefore this made it one of the prime choices for preparing 3D high-energy electrodes, as reported by Torre-

Figure 4. (A) SEM image from LFP/LTO microbattery. Reprinted with permission from^[74]. Copyright (2013) WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim. (B) Graphical illustration of fiber batteries (left) and optical image of textile fibers and electrodes (right). Reprinted with permission from Ref. [58]. Copyright (2017) WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim. (C) Optical images of LFP electrodes prepared by 3D printing with different structures. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [44]. Copyright (2018), American Chemical Society.

Gamarrá *et al.*^[56] In this study, they were able to prepare an 850 μm thickness LCO electrode by FDM. However, the capacity achieved was 100 mAhg^{-1} at $C/12$, which is 36% of the theoretical capacity and lower than that of LFP. Another alternative that can be considered is lithium manganese oxide (LMO) since it has a theoretical capacity of 460 mAhg^{-1} and a voltage of up to 4.5 V.^[80] In contrast, it presents some disadvantages, such as low cycling performance and long-term storage owing to the dissolution of Mn and the decrease in Li-ion diffusion.^[81] Despite these disadvantages, LMO have been prepared by 3D printing several times. For example, a robocasting process, such as the DIW process, was carried out to prepare thick LMO electrodes from highly concentrated aqueous inks.^[55] This study is another example of using 3D printing to prepare thicker electrodes than conventional techniques; however, it also showed poor rate and cycling performance. These materials have not received significant attention in 3D printing applications, and other alternatives such as lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC), have been the main choice for high-energy applications.

NMC is at a mature stage of development because of its use in commercial electric vehicles.^[82] Additionally, the theoretical capacity of NMC is 275 mAhg^{-1} with a voltage above 4.2 V vs Li/Li^+ ,^[83] making it a suitable candidate for preparing high-energy electrodes by 3D printing. However, to meet the current requirements for fast charging, the material structure must be optimized to increase the electrical conductivity and diffusion rate. 3D printing has the potential to improve electrode performance by allowing tuning of the material structure, as demonstrated by Wang *et al.*^[53] In this study, channels of different sizes and distances were created in the NMC electrode (Figure 5A). The results showed that channels with a size of

0.1 mm and a distance of 0.2 mm improved the diffusion rate of lithium ions in the positive electrode, which resulted in higher charge current values of up to 6 C. A similar approach was adopted by Tao *et al.*,^[52] who used DIW to deposit NMC ink on a hot plate. The obtained thick electrodes showed an enhanced diffusion rate, increasing the battery performance at 5 C compared to conventional slurry casting.

3.1.2. Printed Anode Materials

LTO has been one of the earliest materials used for preparing micro batteries and one of the most used electrodes in 3D printing to prepare full cells^[48,78,84] thanks to its zero-volume change and electrochemical stability. Most of the works done focusing on the 3D printing of this material were aimed towards achieving thick electrodes with good kinetics. A good example is the work developed by Liu *et al.*^[59] where they used DIW at low temperatures, to create vertically aligned pores in the electrode structure reducing the transport distance of the ions (Figure 5B).

Graphite is the most common negative material for the conventional slurry casting method due to its high theoretical capacity (372 mAhg^{-1}) and low potential (0.01 V vs Li/Li^+). However, it has not received significant attention in 3D printing applications for preparing full cells, possibly due to its low working potential. Common electrolytes are reduced at this voltage, forming a solid electrolyte interphase (SEI),^[85] which has a significant impact on the performance of conventional electrodes. Thus, it could add a new challenge to the study of complex structures made by 3D printing. Despite this fact, Gastol *et al.*^[86] compared the performances of graphite electro-

Figure 5. (A) Representation of vertically align Li^+ channels for thick NMC electrodes. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [52]. Copyright © 2023 Wiley-VCH GmbH. (B) Top view magnified top view and side view of thick LTO electrode. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [58]. Copyright Copyright © 2022, The Author(s). (C) Front view and side view of thick graphite electrode. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [61]. Copyright © 2022 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V.

des prepared by slurry casting and DIW. They demonstrated the importance of the rheological properties for slurry casting and 3D printing through the introduction of a secondary solvent. This addition enables modification of the graphite microstructure, enhancing Li-ion transport and carbon black dispersion. Furthermore, the 3D-printed electrode exhibited improved cycling performance due to its increased electrical conductivity and lower average tortuosity compared to slurry-based electrodes. Zhang *et al.*^[61] also adopted a similar approach, comparing the performance of slurry casting and direct DIW EESDs. This study examines the impact of varying the number of layers and printing structures on the electrochemical performance of graphite electrodes. The results show that increasing the number of layers results in a higher initial capacity over a given area, indicating no negative influence on lithium diffusion. However, the cycling performance of electrodes with a thickness of 1 mm was poor, while those with a thickness of 0.6 mm demonstrated improved results but were only cycled for a limited period of 60 cycles. Another example of thick graphite electrodes can be found in the study by Xu *et al.*^[62] (Figure 5C). They were able to prepare electrodes with a thickness of 786.7 μm and achieved a capacity of 13.68 mAh cm^{-2} at 0.1 C. However, their results showed poor high-rate performance. Thus, there is a clear trend for standard electrodes based on the preparation of thick electrodes by 3D printing.

With the renewed interest that solid-state batteries have brought to the lithium metal anodes, many have seen in 3D printing technology one way to solve one of its main challenges: dendrite formation. By 3D structuring the current collector it has been observed how the plating/stripping of Li can be significantly enhanced compared to planar current collectors, stabilizing the surface and allowing a stable cycling.^[87,88] This approach is not unique to Li-metal batteries and it has been further used in other chemistries such as aqueous Zn batteries.^[89]

3D printing strategies have also reached sodium chemistry, where the similarities between lithium and sodium electrode materials have facilitated the transition. For example, sodium manganese oxide electrodes behave similarly to LMO, and thanks to the transferable experience it has been used in 3D printing.^[57] While there have been advancements in sodium-ion technologies, they are still in the early stages of development compared to lithium-ion technologies. As such, research on 3D printing for sodium-ion battery electrode materials is currently in its infancy as well.

3.1.3. Nanomaterials for Printed Battery Electrodes

It has been shown that standard electrode materials can make the transition towards printed technologies. However, it is important to stress the fact that these materials at nanoscale along with other novel nanomaterials, have played a crucial role in battery development. The integration of nanomaterials as active material has emerged as a promising electrode alternative, as well as a synergistic option when used as additives.

Nanomaterials are defined as materials that have at least one spatial dimension between 1 and 100 nm. According to their shape can be categorized as zero D, 0D (nanoparticles and quantum dots), 1D (nanotubes and nanorods), and 2D (nanosheets, such as graphene and MXenes).^[90,91] At this scale, materials exhibit unique properties that are not present in their bulk counterparts, even at the microscale.^[92,93] As such, nanomaterials can impart mechanical, optical, thermal, magnetic, and biological properties to 3D printed architectures, such as sensors,^[94,95] antennas,^[96,97] energy storage devices,^[1,63,98] among others. Regarding electrode fabrication, it is widely accepted that nanomaterials improve battery performance due to their low dimensionality, which shortens the ion diffusion path and reduces charge-transfer resistance.^[99–101] In fact, the slow kinetics of Li^+ and e-diffusion in the electrode materials are the main factors hindering the achievement of high-power density batteries.^[101] The mean diffusion time, τ_D , is defined as:

$$\tau_D = \frac{L^2}{2D}$$

where, D and L , are the diffusion coefficient and length, respectively.^[101] Assuming that the commercially available electrode material has an L value of approximately 10 μm , reducing the particle size to the nanoscale range ($< 100 \text{ nm}$) results in a four-order-of-magnitude reduction in the mean diffusion time.^[101] As such, there has been significant research activity on the printing of nanomaterials for battery applications.^[12,17,102] Nanoparticles can also facilitate the use of high-capacity materials in battery electrode fabrication. For instance, transition metal oxide (MO, where M is Co, Ni, Cu, or Fe) nanoparticle anodes can exhibit highly reversible electrochemical capacities as high as 1000 mAh g^{-1} (e.g., Fe_2O_3).^[103,104] The energy storage mechanisms for these materials differ from the classical Li insertion/deinsertion or Li-alloying processes. Transition metal oxides undergo conversion reactions involving the reversible formation and decomposition of Li_2O , accompanying the reduction and oxidation of metal nanoparticles.^[103,105]

where M is a transition metal oxide, such as Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Ru, Cr, Mo, W, etc.^[105] Silicon has also been considered as a suitable alternative to the conventional graphite anode due to its high specific capacity ($\sim 4200 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, lithiated to $\text{Li}_{4.4}\text{Si}$).^[106] However, the use of silicon as an anode material in batteries has been limited due to significant volume variation upon cycling, which leads to electrode pulverization and quick capacity fade.^[107] Over the past decade, several strategies have been developed to alleviate these shortcomings. To prevent electrode pulverization, nanostructures such as nanoparticles, nanolayers, nanowires, and nanotubes have been designed to address Si volume variation.^[66,107,108] As shown in Figure 6A, below a critical size threshold (D_c) of $\sim 150 \text{ nm}$, particle fracture pulverization can be prevented. For example, Beydaghi *et al.*^[65] demonstrated demonstrated the fabrication of Si nanoparticle-based electrodes using a simple and cost-effective FDM

Figure 6. (A) Statistical results confirm a critical size (D_c) around 150 nm. For $D < D_c$ no crack or fracture was observed for the silicon nanoparticles (open stars). When $D > D_c$ particle cracking and fracture were always observed (solid stars). When entering the fracture zone, the ratio of t/D (t, the Li_xSi shell thickness when the first crack appeared) increases (red dots), suggesting a delayed crack event for smaller nanoparticles. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [109]. Copyright (2012) American Chemical Society. (B) Structural and compositional formulation of ink for the 3D printing of battery electrodes. The carbon nanotubes (CNT) and nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC) tightly wrap the active material nanoparticles, thus securing electrical conductivity and enhanced mechanical properties. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [110]. Copyright (2022) Elsevier.

method. The filament in this study consisted of a PLA host polymeric matrix, a mixture of carbon black-doped polypyrrole and wet-jet milling exfoliated few-layer graphene flakes as conductive additives, and Si nanoparticles as the active material. Coin cells were measured in a range of 0.01 and 3 V (vs Li/Li^+) and delivered a specific capacity of up to $\sim 345 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ at a current density of 20 mA g^{-1} . Most importantly, the cells exhibited a high capacitance retention of 96% after 350 cycles at 20 mA g^{-1} .

Mu *et al.* developed a 3D printed free-standing silicon-graphene anode that delivered 8.5 mA h cm^{-2} after 70 cycles with capacity retention of 75.4% and an ultrahigh reversible areal capacity of 16.2 mA h g^{-1} .^[66] In this work, the conventional carbon additives and binders were replaced by graphene, the most popular 2D nanomaterial. Graphene is a suitable nanomaterial for battery applications due to its large surface area ($\sim 2630 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), high electrical conductivity, and Young modulus. It can be used as an electroactive battery material, conductive agent, and support material.^[111] Nanomaterials, including graphene, and their composites are frequently utilized to create functional inks, which simplifies the process of producing batteries with printed cathodes, anodes, and conductive additives.^[16,112,113] For, instance, Kushwaha *et al.*,^[63] successfully inkjet-printed battery anodes using ethanol/cellulose exfoliated graphene. The electrodes demonstrated a high reversible Li storage of approximately 942 mA h g^{-1} at 0.1 C in a

half-cell configuration against Li/Li^+ . The printed film's porous structure results in good electrochemical properties, including a 40% retention of initial capacity even when cycled at 5 C. This is due to an additional reversible surface storage mechanism.^[63] Brown *et al.*, developed a 3D printing method, which integrates inkjet printing and freeze-casting steps, to develop highly porous $\text{MoS}_2/\text{reduced graphene oxide (rGO)}$ electrodes for sodium-ion battery applications. The electrochemical storage processes in this system are attributed to the MoS_2 nanoparticles anchored in the rGO structure, while the carbon framework provides mechanical stability and electrical conductivity. The system achieved a specific capacity of over 429 mA h g^{-1} at 100 mA g^{-1} ($\sim \text{C}/3.3$ rate) within the potential range of 2.5–0.10 V (vs Na^+/Na). 1D nanomaterials and 3D structures based on nanomaterials can also be implemented in the design of printed battery electrodes. For instance, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have a high electrical conductivity, a Young modulus as high as 1.2 TPa, and a tensile strength of 50–200 GPa.^[111] Gupta *et al.*, 3D printed Li-ion battery cathodes based on PLA, LFP, and carbon nanotubes.^[46] Qian *et al.*, developed stretchable DIW-printed batteries based on CNTs, nanocellulose inks, and active materials such as LFP and graphite, as shown in Figure 6B.^[110] The high aspect ratio of CNTs promotes the formation of an electrical and highly flexible network that tightly wraps the particles of the active material.^[110] Due to their ability to easily form 3D woven conductive films, CNTs have been used for printing lightweight current collectors.^[114] As a result, there is significant potential for using CNTs in battery printing for IoT applications and wearable technologies.^[98,110,115,116] More recently, MXene, a relatively new group of 2D transition metal carbides/carbides, has readily stimulated widespread research and technological interest because of its high electrical conductivity, hydrophilicity, and porosity.^[117] MXenes are generally represented by the formula $\text{M}_{n+1}\text{X}_n\text{T}_x$, where M is an early transition metal, X is either C or N, and T_x is a surface termination functional group such as $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{O}$, or $-\text{F}$, with n ranging from 1 to 4.^[32] As for graphene, $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ nanosheets show promise as electrode materials for high electrochemical performance LIBs, due to their high electrical conductivity. Wang *et al.*^[32] ink-jet printed LIBs cathodes composed of heterostructures of V_2O_5 and $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$. The printed cathodes exhibited a high-rate capacity of 112 mA h g^{-1} at 10.5 C and capacity retention of 91.8% after 680 cycles. MXenes can also be used to fabricate current collector-free three-dimensional anodes for LIBs.^[118] MXenes have the potential for use in other chemistries besides LIBs. Wei *et al.*^[119] developed a 3D printed framework comprising nitrogen-doped (N) porous Ti_3C_2 MXenes for Li-S battery applications. In this work, the framework prevents the polysulfide shuttle effect and enhances sulfur electrochemistry. Printed (3D N-p $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{S}$) | 3D N-p $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x@(\text{Li})$ can operate after 250 cycles with a mass loading of 8 mg cm^{-2} .

Nanomaterials are currently a topic of intensive research for battery printing.^[12,17,102] While they hold immense promise for revolutionizing battery technology, they still face several drawbacks that need to be addressed before widespread adoption. The high electroactivity towards lithium storage arising from

nanomaterials' surface-free energy leads to some less-than-desired disadvantages.^[101] Additionally, nanomaterials tend to aggregate or agglomerate. Therefore, they are not as easily mixed with conductive additives and binders, which usually results in higher electrode contact resistances. Moreover, their high surface areas may cause irreversible secondary reactions, leading to poor cyclability and Coulombic efficiency due to electrolyte and electrode degradation. Lastly, electrodes based on nanomaterials exhibit low packing density and, therefore, low volumetric densities. In addition, the cost of currently available nanomaterial inks can be a hindrance to the widespread implementation of printed batteries based on nanomaterials. Despite these shortcomings, the numerous advantages offered by printed nanomaterials in energy storage create the possibility for a wide range of novel EESDs.

3.2. Redox-Active Organic Materials (ROMs)

Organic materials constitute important components of state-of-the-art metal-ion batteries, serving predominantly as electrolytes (e.g. PEO, polypropylene oxide (PPO)), binders (e.g., polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), polyacrylic acid (PAA))^[120] and separators (e.g., polyethylene, polypropylene).^[121] In contrast, inorganic materials currently dominate the energy storage market, serving as both active materials (e.g., transition metal oxides) and conductive addi-

tives (e.g., carbon black, CNTs). However, in the last few years, the use of redox-active organic materials (ROMs) as active material has been gaining momentum, providing alternatives that align with the present energy transition.^[122,123] ROMs-based electrodes exhibit certain challenges, such as currently shorter cycle life, higher self-discharge values, and lower conductivity and energy density compared to electrodes employing inorganic materials. For this reason, ROM-based electrodes generally require higher concentrations of additives. However, ROMs offer several advantages including great flexibility, low volumetric expansion, low toxicity, fast redox chemistry, and simple recycling^[97–99] These properties align very well with the current strategy for printed devices, which are aimed at IoT, wearable technology and smart packaging.

Based on their topology, ROMs can currently be divided into three families (Figure 7A): small molecules, linear polymers, and polymer frameworks^[100] (e.g., covalent organic frameworks (COFs), metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)).^[102,103] Historically, several redox-active small organic molecules have been extensively developed and applied as active materials.^[130] In this regard, the integration of these small molecules into a polymeric structure or a porous framework has been shown to provide novel properties to the material.^[131] These include enhanced chemical, dimensional, and mechanical stability, along with significant flexibility, topology tunability, processability, and versatility.^[132]

Figure 7. (A) Classification of organic battery materials by topology exemplified here through the use of naphthalenetetracarboxylic diimide redox unit. (B) Timeline of the most important discoveries in polymeric LIB cathode materials. Overview of the Li storage performance of the major classes of ROMs electrode materials. (C) Plot of the average discharge potential vs specific capacity Histogram depicting various ROMs produced via additive manufacturing technique, categorized based on (D) their class and (E) the printing technic employed. Example in (B) and (C) reproduced with permission of Ref. [126]. Copyright (2018) Elsevier.

Four notable classes of redox-active polymers for LIBs can be recognized based on the redox mechanism: conducting, organosulfur (among which disulfides stand out), radical, and carbonyl polymers.^[133] These classes are positioned along a timeline of significant discoveries, as shown in Figure 7B. Among these various families, carbonyl compounds (CCs) and conducting polymers (CPs) have garnered significant attention in metal-ion batteries.

CCs serve as suitable active materials owing to their high reversible capacities (Figure 7C). Within these subclasses, quinones and their derivatives have garnered significant interest for Li- or Na-ion batteries. This preference is attributed to their elevated redox potentials, generally above 2.0 V (vs. Li/Li⁺), and higher theoretical capacities when compared to other carbonyl electrodes.^[124,134,135]

On the other hand, owing to their low capacity, high redox potential, and good conductivity, electroactivity, and processability, CPs have been simultaneously used as binders and conducting additives to modify inorganic electrodes. This aims to enhance carrier transport and suppress volume expansion.^[136,137] The most thoroughly researched CPs for non-printed electrodes in metal-ion batteries are poly(3,4-ethylene dioxathiophene) doped with polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS)^[138–140] chosen for its high thermal and chemical stability, as well as anti-solubility.^[141,142] Another notable candidate is polyaniline (PANI)^[143,144] for its inexpensive, easy synthesis, environmental stability, high flexibility, and low cost.^[141,145]

Regarding printed ROMs, it is noteworthy to mention that, to the best of the authors' knowledge, only quinone-based compounds and CPs have been used with additive techniques for metal-ion batteries so far (Figure 7D and Figure 7E). The utilization of quinones as active material by printing has been reported only twice. Additionally, while other CPs, such as PANI or poly(ortho-phenylenediamine) (PoPD), have been used, PEDOT:PSS stands out as the predominant choice for additive manufacturing techniques, serving as a redox-active additive.

3.2.1. Printed Quinone-Based Electrodes

One of the first examples we can find of quinone-based printed electrodes is the work of Leung *et al.*^[68], where dispersed blue 134 anthraquinone (DB), a quinone-type dye small molecule, was utilized as the active material in combination with nano-sized carbon additives and CMC as the binder. They selected DB because of its affordability and capability to generate divalent cations (positive cell reaction) and anions (negative cell reaction) in oxidation and reduction processes, respectively. The electrode slurry was deposited using a "layer-by-layer" AJP technique. The obtained pore honeycomb electrode was studied in both half- and full-cell (symmetric) configurations also using a printed SSE. The symmetric full-cell showed an initial discharge capacity of $\sim 80 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ at 0.5 C ($\sim 48\%$ of its theoretical value: 166 mAh g^{-1}), which then declined rapidly before quasi-stabilizing around 50 mAh g^{-1} at 0.2 C. Although it has been the first reported symmetric solid-state battery based

entirely on organic electrode and electrolyte materials achieving more than 1 V, they concluded that the capacity fading could be addressed through the polymerization of the molecules.^[68]

Building in this direction, Srový *et al.*^[69] developed a polymeric quinone-based electrode using stencil/screen-printing through a mesh. Specifically, poly(anthraquinonyl sulfide) (PAQS) was employed as the active material along with carbon additives and a CMC binder. The electrodes exhibited initial specific capacities of 117 mAh g^{-1} and 127 mAh g^{-1} ($\sim 56\%$ of its theoretical value: 225 mAh g^{-1}) at 0.2 C in Li-ion and Na-ion half-cells, respectively, with a capacity retention of 76% after 550 cycles in the case of Li-ion.^[54] In comparison, non-printed PAQS is capable of obtaining a substantially higher capacity of 198 mAh g^{-1} and capacity retention of 90% after 200 cycles.^[146] Finally, they developed fully printed batteries using a roll-to-roll process in a full-cell configuration employing PAQS based anode and LMO-based cathode (Figure 8). Notably, the cell was assembled in an air atmosphere, achieving a capacity of 57 mAh g^{-1} at a rate of 0.2 C, with a good capacity retention of 61% after 100 cycles.^[69]

3.2.2. Printed CP-Based Electrodes

In recent years, CPs have been extensively used with additive techniques for several applications.^[141,147] Despite this progress, CPs often differ from the standard mechanical properties and processing characteristics of thermoplastic polymers due to their insoluble and infusible powder form. Consequently, CPs pose unique challenges across different additive manufacturing methods, as they need specific rheological properties to be processed effectively.^[147] These challenges will be addressed in the following subsections:

3.2.2.1. CPs for Jetting-Based Techniques

CPs require inks with low viscosity to ensure accurate deposition and minimize shear forces during ejection. This facilitates the integration of CPs into solvent- or water-based inks, although challenges persist due to the inherently low solubility

Figure 8. A) R2R fully printed PAQS/LMO battery, Structure of the layers of R2R printed battery (B) Roll of printed battery with electrodes PAQS/LMO. Reprinted with permission of Ref. [69]. Copyright (2021) Elsevier.

of some CPs.^[147] Lawes *et al.*^[34] compared PEDOT:PSS, which exhibits remarkable dispersibility compared to other typical conductive additives^[148], with other binders such as PVP, CMC, and Na-alginate for IJP printed anodes consisting of silicon nanoparticles (SiNPs). To ensure the same printing conditions, they used similar viscosities (around 10 mPas) for each binder obtaining a smooth deposition with the PEDOT:PSS ink. They concluded that PEDOT:PSS exhibited higher capacities and more stable cycling compared to the rest of the binders, as shown in Figure 9A. This is attributed to its high electrical conductivity and reversible deformation during SiNPs expansion and contraction, ensuring that the SiNPs do not become electrically isolated (Figure 9B).^[34]

3.2.2.2. CPs for Light-Based Techniques

A similar electrode configuration was printed by DLP by Xinliang Ye *et al.*^[64] Since light-based techniques are required to combine electrode materials with photocurable resins, they developed a honeycomb microstructured anode with SNPs embedded in a polymeric matrix composed of PEDOT:PSS and a photocurable polyethylene glycol (PEG)-based hydrogel. The

SiNPs/PEDOT:PSS/PEG (4:1:12 wt.%) electrode achieved a better electrochemical performance than a traditional Si electrode.^[64] This improvement can be attributed to both the reversible deformation effect of PEDOT as described earlier by Lawes^[34] and the DLP honeycomb structure that enabled the accommodation of the volume expansion.

3.2.2.3. CPs for Filament Based Techniques

On the other hand, filament-based techniques such as DIW and FDM require inks with high viscosity and shape retention. Bao P. *et al.*^[51] showed that adding PEDOT:PSS to an LFP-CMC-based ink improved the printability in terms of shape retention for DIW stacked architectures when increasing the number of layers. A double-layer electrode exhibited a notable capacity of 155.9 mAh g⁻¹, retaining 92% of its initial capacity after 100 cycles, and experiencing a mere 30% capacity loss when the electrode was extended to 12 layers.

FDM case presents increased complexity due to the necessity of using polymers in a semi-molten state. As pristine CPs lack the necessary rheological characteristics, new strategies are required to enable the use of thermoplastics in blends or copolymers for effective extrusion-based printing^[147]. In this way, an alternative method to indirectly achieve 3D structures with CPs has been proposed. This involves a post-printing electrodeposition process, wherein CPs are deposited around the surface of a 3D-printed carbon framework in a thermoplastic medium via FDM. First, Wanli Gao *et al.*^[54] utilized this approach to fabricate a 0D carbon-based filament network (ODCFN) embedded in PLA with LMO. After chemically removing the insulating PLA, PoPD was incorporated into the structure by electrodeposition (Figure 10A and Figure 10B). The resulting 3D@PoPD@LMO electrode exhibited a significantly improved capacity for LIBs, compared to the 3D@LMO electrode (Figure 10C).^[54] Similarly, Wanli Gao *et al.*^[70] also electrodeposited PAA-doped PANI, around a 1DCFN embedded in PLA for aqueous zinc ion batteries (ZIBs).^[70] The 3D@PANI-PAA's cycling values align with those typically observed for non-printed ZIB electrodes (Figure 10D).^[70]

Figure 9. (A) Cycling performance at 0.1 C of inkjet-printed silicon anodes prepared with four different polymer binders. (B) Schematic illustration of the proposed mechanism explaining the electrochemical performance of anodes prepared with different binders. Contrary to other binders, with PEDOT:PSS, the SiNPs remain electrically connected throughout charging/discharging and are therefore able to maintain a stable cycling capacity. Reprinted with permission of Ref. [34]. Copyright (2017) Elsevier.

3.3.3. Printed COFs and MOFs Based Electrodes

Both COFs and MOFs have undergone testing as redox-active materials for metal-ion batteries on several occasions.^[149–152] However, to the author's knowledge, neither the COFs nor the MOFs with redox-active organic parts have yet been printed for metal-ion batteries.

It is worth noting that MOFs have been indeed printed as hierarchically porous structured electrodes for LIBs batteries by DIW such as Cu-MOFs,^[153] Zn-MOFs,^[154] and Al-MOFs.^[155] Nevertheless, the organic compound of the MOF was electrochemically inactive in every case, acting just as linkers.^[150] Thus, in this review, we are not considering those examples inside of the ROMs category.

Figure 10. Schematic illustrations of charge transfer difference between (A) activated 3D-printed and (B) PoPD-refilled carbon electrode. Arrows indicate the efficient omnidirectional charge transfer among all carbon particles including the isolated ones after conductive PoPD electrodeposition. (C) Comparison of rate performance between 3D@LMO and 3D@PoPD@LMO electrodes. (D) Comparison of rate performance between 3D@PANI-PAA cathode and other organic cathodes for aqueous Zn-ion batteries. Examples in (A), (B), and (C) are reproduced with permission of Ref. [54]. Copyright (2021) Wiley. Example in (D) reproduced with permission of Ref. [70]. Copyright (2022) Elsevier.

4. Printed Electrolytes

In the framework of printed devices and considering the advantages that the 3D structured batteries provide to the solid-state batteries including reduced stress and better ion flow,^[156] the trend leads to the fully printed fully solid batteries. In this regard, there are three main types of SEs: polymeric, ceramic, and a combination of both, the composite electrolytes. Although these seem to be the long-term future of printed batteries, there is still a myriad of problems that plague the practical integration of those strategies, such as low ionic conductivities and hard electrode/electrolyte interfaces.^[157] Therefore at the moment, there is a more common hybrid approach that consists of the gelation or containment of liquid electrolytes in solid or semi-solid matrixes.^[24] This is the case of the quasi-solid-state or gel electrolytes. The four types of solid SEs are further described in the following subsections.

4.1. Quasi-Solid-State Electrolytes

QSEs are a broad family of electrolytes that are composed of a combination of a liquid electrolyte and a solid matrix. In this type of electrolyte, the solid matrix plays a minimal role in the ion conduction process, and its function is just the containment of the electrolyte and the prevention of a short-circuit in a similar manner as the separator in regular batteries. This is the most common approach in printed devices as the chemistry is well known, the ionic conductivity is very good, and the process is straightforward. There are two differentiated strategies for the printing of QSEs: The first one, is the formulation of a

printable ink with all the components already in (solid matrix, solvent, and salt), and the second one, is printing the solid matrix first and then infiltrating liquid electrolyte.

Regarding the first approach, if the solvent of the electrolyte is a common battery solvent such as ethylene carbonate (EC) these are known as gel-SEs, and if an ionic liquid is known as ionogel-SEs.^[24] A few of these examples are the photocurable ionogel-SE developed by Gambe et al.^[158] or the gel-SE printed by SLA by Qiming et al.^[159] The second route for obtaining QSEs, is based on the infiltration of pre-printed solid matrixes which is also commonly referred to as 3D printed separators due to the similarity of their workflow and role to the common battery separators. These have been widely employed in batteries of different chemistries such as the hydrogel for Zn-ion batteries prepared by DLP by Poompiew et al.^[160] or the highly thermoresistant Al₂O₃-PVDF-based QSE printed by DIW prepared by Blake et al.^[161] for Li-ion batteries. In all types of QSEs, the solid matrix can be a polymeric one such as polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), and/or some kind of ceramic insulating filler such as SiO₂ or Al₂O₃.

4.2. Solid Polymeric Electrolytes

SPEs are composed of a polymer matrix and a dissolved lithium salt. There are different types of polymeric matrixes all broadly organized around four families: PEO-based, Polycarbonate-based, Polysiloxane-based, and Plastic crystal-based.^[162] Although all have slightly different properties, advantages, and disadvantages, the attractiveness of the SPEs is centered around their easy processability, flexibility, and printability. This allows the creation of completely new concepts of batteries with exciting functionalities such as the coaxial cable battery for which Ragones et al. proposed the use of PEO-based electrolyte mixed with PLA for its printing by FDM.^[25] The ionic conductivity and transfer number of SPEs tend to be significantly lower than the liquid and ceramic electrolytes but on the contrary, the interfaces formed with the cathode/anode are generally much better than those with ceramic ones. This is further enhanced with the use of printing methodologies such as the case of Deiner et al. where they used AJP to deposit PEO-based SPEs with different salts on top of LFP cathodes,^[163] or the work of Lopez-Hallman et al. where similarly used AJP to deposit and infiltrate the SPE on the cathode to later crosslink it with UV light.^[38] Reversely, their stability with Li metal and its inhomogeneous plating is still lacking and that is why are not so common the use of SPEs with Li-metal.^[24,164] Still, this type of solid electrolytes, especially the PEO-based, are the most common choice for fully solid printed batteries due to their easy processability and the good interfaces achievable. SPEs are also the most common type of solid electrolyte in industry although their presence is minimal compared to liquid electrolytes.^[164] The main direction of the SPE field in the last years has been to overcome the limitations of the state-of-the-art SPEs. This includes mainly the PEO but also PAN, PVDF, and PMMA-based electrolytes although these have been mainly used for gel-SE.^[165] PEO's low electrochemical window (<3.9 V)

and limited ionic conductivity restrict the active material choice, performance, and end application.^[166] This has led to the development of alternative SPEs such as polycarbonates,^[162] hybridization with other polymers,^[166] PEO modification,^[167] and the formation of composite SEs (further described in section 4.4).^[165] Although these approaches have produced important improvements, in the printing field, PEO-based SPEs are still the main choice due to their benchmark role^[168] and well-known properties which are an asset in the first steps of an incipient technology such as the 3D printed batteries. It is expected that as the technology maturity improves, further innovations in SPEs will reach the field.

4.3. Solid Ceramic Electrolytes

This family of electrolytes can be further divided into oxide and sulfide SEs. Their main advantage is the high ionic conductivity and broad temperature operational range, which opens exciting new opportunities for battery usage in harsh environments.^[13] However, there are still many challenges for their implementation including the instabilities at the interfaces and the physical contact with the electrode. This is however a lengthy discussion and not the aim of this review, thus further information can be obtained elsewhere.^[157,169] The challenges regarding printed devices revolve around their practical incorporation into devices. One of the issues is the need for a sintering step which requires the adaptation of the printing workflow to adapt it to the device printing. For this reason, is a common approach to print self-standing SCEs such as the work done by Sabato et. al. where they printed by SLA a 3D Lithium Aluminum Germanium Phosphate ($\text{Li}_{1.5}\text{Al}_{0.5}\text{Ge}_{1.5}\text{P}_3\text{O}_{12}$, LAGP)^[21] or similar works with DIW,^[26] IJP^[170], and SLA templates.^[19] Due to the good stability of ceramic electrolytes with Li metal, this type of electrolyte is generally used with Li anode whose surface can adapt well to the pre-printed electrolytes, and the cathode is printed on top of the ceramic.^[171] This however can bring up high electrode-electrolyte impedance at the interface and to reduce this issue and integrate the cathode during the sintering step, a significant effort has been made to develop low-temperature sintering ceramics.^[172]

4.4. Composite or Hybrid Solid Electrolytes

A composite solid electrolyte (CSE) is understood as a combination of a solid polymeric and solid ceramic electrolyte. Sometimes is also defined as CSE the combination of an SPE with a ceramic filler. This is generally done to improve the mechanical properties of the blend as well as to depress the polymer crystallinity promoting ionic conduction.^[162] In this approach the ceramic filler has no role regarding the ion transport, thus in this review, we will not consider these cases as CSEs.

The hybridization of the organic-inorganic ion conductors aims to combine the strengths of both types of materials, creating an easily processable and flexible solid electrolyte with

high ionic conductivity through the ceramic phase.^[172] These combinations are usually done to add further functionalities or solve issues of the individual components depending on the selected materials. For instance, it is common the use lithium lanthanum zirconium oxide ($\text{Li}_{7-3x}\text{Al}_x\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$, LLZO) in CSEs to improve the stability of the hybrid with the Li anode.^[173] This strategy has been recently followed by Lechartier et al.^[174] to create photocurable CSE with LLZO concentration as high as 40% and ionic conductivities around $10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. With sulfide-type ceramics it typically follows the opposite strategy, creating a “polymer in ceramic” electrolyte to improve the stability of the sulfide-electrolyte while trying to maintain the ceramic concentration as high as possible.^[173]

5. Summary and Outlook

Thanks to the low prototyping cost of the printing strategies, in the last years we have seen a rise in the works using different printing technologies. The trend has been moving from planar and thin film printing to more advanced 3D structures where classical coating methodologies such as spin and spray coating have been displaced in favor of filament-, jetting- and light-based techniques. Among the printing technologies, the most used in literature is FDM, Figure 11. The produced electrodes and electrolytes are structurally very robust and is therefore easy to obtain self-standing pieces with good mechanical properties. Additionally, the widespread availability and low cost of FDM printers have further play a role in its popularity. FDM is closely followed by DIW, Figure 11, in which the minimal changes necessary to the ink compared to common slurry deposition, make it an accessible way to produce 3D architectures. In the very last few years techniques such as AJP and light-based ones have seen an increase in their use for active components as some of the challenges associated with the techniques have been mitigated. For instance, the post-

Figure 11. Bibliographic data on the number of publications of 3D printed batteries by technique. The information was obtained through the API key from Scopus and the essay library from Python. The term 3D printing battery was used to search the papers and the results were filtered by Articles. 519 articles were found, and it was possible to access 238 articles to find keywords related to each technique. The keywords used by technique were: AJP and aerosol jet printing; FDM, FFF; fused filament fabrication and fused deposition modeling; DIW and direct ink writing; SLA and stereolithography; DLP and digital light processing.

processing in the light-based or as deposition with assisted drying in the AJP has helped with the improved performance.^[21,30]

Material-wise, a huge effort has been made to adapt common materials and inks to their implementation in printed devices. Due to how driven 3D printing is by sustainability, most of the work in the field has been focused on the use of LFP as cathode material and only high-energy applications have been using NMC and LCO. Regarding the anode choices, LTO has received significantly more attention in 3D printing than typical alternatives such as graphite due to its zero-volume expansion, especially in solid-state batteries.

One of the main reasons for the use of 3D printing strategies with standard types of materials has been the higher thicknesses achievable compared to slurry cast procedures. This allows higher energy densities compared with typical electrodes even without the use of advanced architectures (Figure 12).

Nanomaterials have been found in 3D printing as a natural ally. Despite their high promises, nanomaterials have not entered yet the production lines of state-of-the-art batteries, and their low maturity has only made them reach some niche fields such as IoT applications and wearables. One of their main limitations is the upscaling of nanomaterial-based battery electrodes. They suffer from the lack of standardized metrics and a plethora of materials synthesis routes, that might not be compatible with regular, industrial production lines. In this regard, their combination with 3D printing has been ideal both in the material processing perspective as well as in the application perspective. Some printing methodologies such as IJP have insurmountable limitations on material size and ink rheology, and nanomaterial-based colloidal dispersions are a perfect fit for them. This also applies to applications such as micro batteries, where the higher gravimetric capacities of the nanomaterials, their easy processability in inks, and extra functionalities such as flexibility compensate for their higher cost (Figure 12). Of course, the integration of nanomaterial-based printed devices is not free of challenges, and issues such as tab detachment from carbon substrates are still problematic.

With the push for sustainable choices for energy storage materials, ROMs have been gaining momentum lately. Although CCs are largely unexplored for printed devices and only a few quinone-based examples exist, it is expected that their popularity will boom in the next few years. This is due to the rise of fields like smart packaging where the high volume requires a sustainable and cheap power source whose performances are not necessarily very high. Due to their sheer number, the waste management of this type of application is very challenging thus easy recycling or non-toxic degradation is a priority for the materials that compose them (Figure 12).^[175] Reversely, CPs have been extensively used in printed electrodes. Their approach is very different from that of the CCs and is generally used as redox-active binders and conductive additives with high-performing materials such as nanomaterials. Their high cost prevents its wide adoption thus their integration is aimed at niche applications similar to nanomaterials and mostly accompanying them.

Regarding printed electrolytes, since there are no commercial solid-state batteries that can serve as a reference for the industrially preferred type of solid electrolyte, it is not clear whether ceramic or polymeric SEs will become the main choice. It is likely that once the first solid-state batteries are commercially available, the printing field will adopt its electrolyte choice too. For now, polymeric, and composite SEs seem to be the most promising thanks to their easy printability and good interfaces. Additionally, they align well with some of the extra functionalities that are desired for printed devices, such as flexibility, and require minimal post-processing treatments. Still, fully SEs cannot compete in performance with liquid electrolytes, and thus QSEs are still the preferred way to achieve fully printed batteries.

This field is rapidly evolving and heavily influenced by the trends marked by the EV sector. We are now at a crossroads between different technologies, and after the market deployment of solid-state batteries takes place, we will see a massive boom in the interest in the use of 3D printing strategies for their production.

Figure 12. Schematic summary of the main advantages that the 3D printing technology brings to each of the electrode material class and the main applications for which each family is being proposed.

6. Abbreviations

ODCFN	Zero-Dimensional Carbon-based Filament Network
ABS	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
AJP	Aerosol Jet Printing
AM	Additive Manufacturing
CCs	Carbonyl Compounds
CMC	Carboxymethyl Cellulose
CNTs	Carbon Nanotubes
COFs	Covalent Organic Frameworks
CPs	Conducting Polymers
CSEs	Composite Solid Electrolytes
DB	Disperse Blue 134 anthraquinone
DIW	Direct Ink Writing
EC	Ethylene Carbonate
EESDs	Electrochemical Energy Storage Devices
ESD	Energy Storage Device
EVs	Electric Vehicles
FDM	Fused Deposition Modeling
IJP	Inkjet Printing
IoT	Internet of Things
LAGP	Lithium Aluminum Germanium Phosphate
LCO	Lithium Cobalt Oxide
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
LIBs	Lithium-Ion Batteries
LLZO	Lithium Lanthanum Zirconium Oxide
LMO	Lithium Manganese Oxide
LTO	Lithium Titanate
MOFs	Metal-Organic Frameworks
•NCA	Lithium Nickel Cobalt Aluminum Oxide
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide
PAA	Polyacrylic Acid
PANI	Polyaniline
PAQS	Poly (anthraquinone sulfide)
PC	Polycarbonate
PEDOT:PSS	Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) Polystyrene Sulfonate
PEG	Polyethylene Glycol
PEO	Polyethylene Oxide
PLA	Poly(lactic Acid)
PoPD	Poly(ortho-phenylenediamine)
PPO	Polypropylene Oxide
PVDF	Polyvinylidene Fluoride
PVA	Polyvinyl Alcohol
QSEs	Quasi-Solid Electrolytes
rGO	Reduced Graphene Oxide
ROMs	Redox-Active Organic Materials
SEI	Solid Electrolyte Interphase
SEs	Solid Electrolytes
SiNPs	Silicon Nanoparticles
SLA	Stereolithography
SLS	Selective Laser Sintering
SPEs	Solid Polymeric Electrolytes
UV	Ultraviolet
ZIBs	Zinc Ion Batteries

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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REVIEW

3D printing of batteries, also known as additive manufacturing, has the potential to create flexible, smaller, lighter, and more cost-effective batteries than those currently available. This review presents the latest advances in electroactive materials, deposition methods, and electrolyte choices for advanced printed batteries.

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Materials for 3D Printed Metal and Metal-Ion Batteries